

EBT Evaluation Template for TEBT-2024-0006

Version	17 June 2024	Assessing the Effects of a Precommitment Policy Applied During Peer Review
Submission Title		
Submission Reference	TEBT-2024-0006	
Handling Editor	Olwenn Martin, ORCID: 0000-0003-2724-7882	
Number of Reviewers	2	
Submission Type	Research Letter	
Preprint DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11122252	
Status	In Peer-Review	
Evaluation Date	17 June 2024	
Evaluation Round	Peer review round 1	
Recommendation	Revise	
Handling Editor's Explanation for Recommendation	This manuscript was reviewed positively. The main comments received were related to demand for a more detailed description of the overall project and limitations of the approach, as well as possibility to improve the clarity of the language in places.	

Summary of article and editor recommendations

This submission is a research letter that gives an overview of a planned meta-experiment in journal publishing. Specifically, this meta-experiment across journals aims to investigate the impact of precommitment to publish if an agreed revision plan is adhered to. Overall, this manuscript was reviewed positively. The main comments received were related to demand for a more detailed description of the overall project and its limitations. Additionally, the clarity of the language may be improved in places.

KEY: R = Revisions recommended. N 1. Clarity of knowledge goals

= No issues identified at this time. X

= Not applicable. Domain

Evaluation Question

Are the research questions important and clearly articulated?

Answer

Strongly Agree

Specific Issues

N Currency and relevance of the topic to scientific discourse

N Clarity about knowledge goals or hypotheses of the research

R Justification for conducting the research (context, rationale, impact)

Summary of comments

Reviewers concurred on the innovativeness of the proposed approach and commended the authors on launching this initiative. The justification for conducting the research could be improved by informing its context through an overview of the literature on editorial innovations.

1. I recommend to publish this paper. The meta experiment sounds great. I applaud Evidence-Based Toxicology for taking part in this initiative.

Thank you for the praise! We are very excited about the ideas we are developing in the project, and it is great to see others interested as well.

2. I provide this review as an academic passionate about open scholarship, and, to be very explicit, no expertise in toxicology. I hope that this review is of benefit to you the authors in

providing constructive feedback as to how to maximise the communicative value of your message. First off I'd like to comment that the idea of Registered Revisions is an interesting one, and whilst I'm not convinced that this is the ideal solution to the issues with publication highlighted (and rightfully so given the absence of evidence), I certainly see the appeal of this, especially given that I have implemented other such innovations in journals I am EiC/AE for (e.g., publication of verification reports at the journal of open psychology data). I also see the value of encouraging and demonstrating the potential of editorial innovations across journals. As such, I commend the authors for coming up with an innovative approach to tackling some of the persistent issues with peer-review during publication. I also commend the authors for planning such an ambitious project working across journals to evaluate practice.

We completely agree that the Registered Revisions policy is not a singular ideal solution for a very complex problem. We believe it to be a patch for a particular set of circumstances. More importantly, both the Registered Revisions policy itself and the style of experimental evidence generation are stepping stones toward larger goals.

We have added the following to emphasize this (new text in italics):

“The Registered Revisions policy itself is an incremental policy reform rather than a comprehensive fix to the shortcomings of our current publication system. It occurs during the traditional peer review process, does not require new publication formats or a major change in the conduct of research practice, requires relatively little change to new processes and procedures, and allows for variation in how requests for new additional data or analysis occur at different journals. Takeup of precommitment devices like preregistration and Registered Reports is hampered by requiring the researchers to know what these devices are, to be willing to change their behaviors, and be willing to take risks on something new. Registered Revisions introduces precommitment devices during the course of standard journal review, shifting the impetus for change to journals. The policy provides a restructuring of the revision process that allows researchers to engage in precommitment in a low-risk, capacity-efficient way. We hope it provides a stepping stone toward more comprehensive reforms and formats, such as Registered Reports. Most importantly, we believe that we have created a way to find out if and how well it works on a variety of dimensions, ranging from research burden, satisfaction, and the quality and reliability of subsequent research.”

3. Given the theme of new editorial practices, it was surprising not to see reference to papers exploring editorial developments and innovations e.g., that of Silverstein et al. 2024 (Silverstein, P., Elman, C., Montoya, A., McGillivray, B., Pennington, C. R., Harrison, C. H., ... & Syed, M. (2024). A guide for social science journal editors on easing into open science. *Research integrity and peer review*, 9(1), 2.) that touch upon the issues discussed. As a COI, I'm an author on this paper and I'd like to be explicit in noting that I'm not expecting this to be cited and this has no impact upon my recommendations for this manuscript. I'm more just raising the view that a more holistic picture of editorial innovations might help contextualise the current developments

more accurately. I appreciate there may be journal limits imposed but there are few citations to help contextualise the work.

Thank you for pointing this out; we agree that this is missing context within the larger science reform movement, as well as missing relevant reference to other randomized experiments. We have added some text in conjunction with the comments from Question 4 below.

Suggestions for addressing the comments:

Consider expanding the introduction describing the context for the meta-experiment by briefly reviewing editorial innovations across disciplines.

Domain	2. Strength of argument for the approach
Evaluation	Do the authors present a logical, rational, and/or plausible approach to achieving their research goals?
Question	goals?
Answer	Somewhat Disagree
Specific	R Theory as to how the experiment delivers the knowledge goal
Issues	R Identification and authentication of experimental components R Acknowledgement of limitations of the approach
Summary of comments	Reviewers made several suggestions to improve the clarity and strength of the argument for the proposed approach. Specifically, the manuscript would benefit for including more details of the wider project and what would be expected of a revision plan, incentives for journal editors to participate and a discussion of the limitations of the approach.

4. Some more details on the wider project may be of benefit e.g., what journals are included and why.

We have added the following text to the discussion section make this clearer

“Many of the early pathfinder journal partners are based in the social sciences, biology, and medicine, in large part due to direct human impact and having communities that are relatively actively engaged in open science and institutional reform (Ferguson et al. 2023; Silverstein et al. 2024; Hair et al. 2019; Cobo et al. 2011). Evidence Based Toxicology is among the two first pilots launched, and has had a key role co-designing and iterating on the implementation and logistical design of this project.”

5. A little more structure/detail in what would be expected of a revision plan will help with consistency in application. With developments like preregistration, I feel the outcomes are only as good as the implementation. More details on this might help increase practical uptake and provide a template/framework from which others can see the value of what is being proposed.

We agree that more detail is warranted here. There is a somewhat complicated relationship at play here; because different fields and even journals within fields have strongly differing publication institutions, policies, and procedures, this project is designed with a large amount of flexibility in exactly how it is implemented. That said, we are developing a “default” workflow which journals can modify to their particular needs, and we can certainly give more detail on that workflow.

To address this we have added a workflow diagram and brief description to the main text and a series of procedural references and templates to the supplements. The addition to the main text is below:

Figure 1: Trial workflow

“The expected workflow for both the Registered Revisions policy and the trial itself are expected to vary substantially between fields and journals. We have developed and are testing an infrastructure and workflow that we believe to be reasonably generalizable and adaptable to a wide range of scenarios. A general diagram of the workflow for Registered Revisions is provided in Figure 1. We have also provided a full example workflow hosted on an Open Science Framework (OSF) project for this study (Haber et al. 2023). This includes a procedural reference, templates and instructions for communication with and between authors and peer reviewers, and data entry infrastructure. Note that these are for demonstration purposes only at this time.”

6. You note that the primary outcome is 'time' but given the focus of much of these open science innovations is research quality, it'd be interesting to include more of a discussion/justification of the chosen outcomes.

“There are three key categories of outcomes in this trial: (1) procedural outcomes with the peer review process itself, (2) research reliability outcomes related to the outputs of the manuscripts reviewed, and (3) perceptual outcomes having to do with how authors, reviewers, and editors experience the policy and trial. Among those, the procedural outcomes are our primary outcomes for both feasibility and interpretability. Time to event outcomes are continuous outcomes that differ for each submission, and are relatively straightforward to interpret, particularly from a casual perspective. Process outcomes are also typically the primary interest of journals and publishers, who may be concerned about workloads or procedural backlogs.

While research reliability outcomes are a strong interest, indicators of it (such as an increase in the proportion of null results) are binary, likely to be relatively small differences between arms, and conditional on the downstream causal effects of the trial arm. This makes them comparatively less powered and more difficult to measure and interpret. Finally, the perceptual outcomes will provide key subjective data that will inform implementability at scale largely through qualitative assessment.”

7. On p3 you discuss the challenges with implementation and testing of this practice and I think it'd be of great value to expand upon this a little more. For example, why would they need a similar launch schedule?

We were unclear on this point, and appreciate the comment. This was intended to refer to more typical trial approaches, which generally occur at a fairly synced time schedule even for multi-center trials. Syncing is not true for our meta experiment, which is a key design innovation here. To help clarify, we have added the following:

“Under standard approaches to large scale trials, this would typically require a relatively large sample size and a large consortium of journals...”

8. I have one small comment. The authors state that "participating journal editors would only be rewarded by being the nth author on a publication, reducing incentives to go out on a limb for a time consuming, difficult, and somewhat risky proposition". This doesn't make sense to me. In my view the main reward for participating journal editors is not an additional publication, but the recognition they will get from the academic community for the contribution they are making to improving peer review practices.

We have combined this comment with the comment below for responses.

9. I think also assuming that authorship on a paper is the only outcome is a little reductionist given that many editors happily engage in open scholarship innovations due to the value they consider to add to the process, to their values, to the outcomes of their journal, etc.

We agree that this was perhaps too reductionist and lacked important nuance and the contribution of social influences, particularly among early adopters. That said, we believe

that mass adoption relies on more direct, tangible, and immediate career incentives in addition to those social forces. We have modified this section as follows:

“In the end, participating journal editors’ *most direct career-sustaining reward* would be the nth author on a publication, reducing incentives to go out on a limb for a time consuming, difficult, and somewhat risky proposition. *Different editors and institutions have a multitude of motivations. While many early adopters may be motivated to navigate these challenges due to a desire to improve scholarly communication systems, we are pairing this with more tangible - albeit nominal - incentives suitable for policy adoption at scale.*”

Suggestions for addressing the comments:

Whilst this is a research letter rather than a fully-fledged protocol, the manuscript would nonetheless benefit from the inclusion of more details of about the proposed approach. Particularly, consider the reviewers’ comments above and describe in more detail about the wider project such as the rationale for inclusion of journals in this initiative as well as an expanded description of what would be expected of a revision plan. Do also consider incentives for journal editors to participate beyond co-authorship in a publication and a discussion of the selection of outcomes and the limitations of the proposed approach.

Domain	3. Reader engagement
Evaluation Question	Is the article written in an accessible and engaging style?
Answer	Neither Agree nor Disagree
Specific Issues	N Use of jargon and technical language N Tone N Personal connection
Summary of comments	There were no specific comments relevant to reader engagement. Some minor issues with clarity of language are mentioned in the subsequent “Length and language” domain. Overall, reviewers engaged with the manuscript as submitted.

Domain	4. Length and language
Evaluation Question	Is the article of appropriate length and linguistic accuracy?
Answer	Somewhat Disagree
Specific Issues	N Length R Ease of reading for non-native speaker
Summary of comments	A few minors issues with the clarity of language have been highlighted.

10. Some issues with clarity in wording e.g., "Authors are asked to make a Revision Plan for how they will address these comments, and*,* if approved*,* editors agree to make an in principle acceptance for publication decision on the basis of this Revision Plan". Similarly what

is referred to here: "This approach may lower the barrier to conducting metascientific investigations for evidence-informed journal policy reform" is unclear. "As we encounter intensifying systemic issues with the reliability, utility, and incentives of publication, we must engage in reform and rethinking of journal policy and implementation" - this phrasing suggests the issues are new rather than the attention paid to these issues has recently increased. There are a few areas like this in the manuscript which could be clarified with more explicit wording.

“Authors are asked to make a Revision Plan for how they will address these comments. If the Revision Plan and responses to standard questions are approved, editors agree to make an in-principle acceptance for publication decision. In other words, the article will be accepted as long as the Revision Plan is carried out as specified, regardless of the results.”

“This approach presents a potential path forward for evidence-informed journal policy reform at scale.”

“Systemic issues with the reliability, utility, and incentives of scientific publication are intensifying. To counter this, we must engage in reform and rethinking of journal policy and implementation.”

We have additionally made numerous other word tweaks throughout the document

Suggestions for addressing the comments:

Whilst revising the manuscript, please review the clarity of language throughout.

Additional comments and suggestions for revision

11. A core reservation on the publication of this manuscript here is the choice of journal outlet itself. It's unclear why this work is being submitted to this journal as the content does not refer to toxicology - I appreciate the journal is going to be one journal running this scheme but why is it best this be disseminated in this journal rather than a more meta-science or research integrity based journal (e.g., Research Integrity and Peer Review, to pick one from the top of my head) where you might be able to provide a more detailed account of the project? It then adds other questions e.g., why is toxicology a key area targeted by this scheme? Where are the details of the process e.g., the evaluation scope? Whilst I appreciate the need to launch the initiative it does feel like this might be better suited elsewhere. I note that the EiC of the journal is an author in this manuscript so appreciate this comment is likely to make the decision of the AE slightly more complex and my apologies to all parties for this!

We agree that research integrity and related journals would also be appropriate for this piece.

Evidence-Based Toxicology was chosen as the most appropriate outlet for this letter due both to its critical and outsized role and influence in the development of the pathfinding

pilots and being among the first two journals to launch. We believe there is value in publishing an introduction to the project in one of the participating journals.

Later publications detailing our experience during the pilots and initial results will most likely be placed in more research integrity-related and/or general scientific journals.

To reflect this, we have added the following

“Evidence Based Toxicology is among the two first pilots launched, and has had a key role co-designing and iterating on the implementation and logistical design of this project.”